

Contributions of Phytogetic Foods Safety and Nutritional Practices to the Fight Against COVID-19 in the African Region

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Abstract

Undeniably, and still painful is the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human health, societies, and the economies world over, and the African region. The COVID-19 burden is uneven and the variation in incidences across countries is driven by socio-ecological factors, likewise, the severity and risk of mortality after infection are influenced by biophysical factors. Imputed public health response measures and health system responses contributed significantly to minimising the above factors. Notwithstanding, the observed relatively fewer dead cases in the African region vis-à-vis other regions of the world may be linked to natural availability and socio-economic access to phytogetic foods, as well as food safety and healthy nutritional practices. This review has briefly discussed the roles of phytogetic food safety and nutritional practices vis-à-vis the fight against COVID-19. In brief, phytogetic foods appear to be a promising option to fight against COVID-19 as they are known to contain vital flavonoids and antioxidants. When considering that a good immune system helps to fight against the virus, the boost of immunity requires eating a nutritious diet as the immune system relies on a steady supply of nutrients to work well. These nutrients are better taken whole (than in supplements) with food safety observed.

Keywords: phytogetic foods, food safety, nutritional practices, COVID-19

1. Introduction: Coronavirus and The African region

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human health, societies, and the economies world over, and the African region non-exclusive is still painful. “Globally, as of 6:14 pm CET, 3 February 2023, there have been 754,018,841 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 6,817,478 deaths, reported to WHO, and as of 31 January 2023, a total of 13,168,935,724 vaccine doses have been administered.” (WHO, 2023). Although little is available on the World Wide Web concerning the way of occurrence, spread, death, and management of COVID-19 in the African region (Onafeso *et al.*, 2021), the African region has relatively fewer deaths from the COVID-19 infections compared to other regions of the world (Cabore *et al.*, 2022).

In the world, and the African region, the COVID-19 burden is uneven and the variation in the number of infections within and across countries is compelled by socio-ecological factors (such as population density, age, and hygiene), whilst the number of deaths is driven by biophysical factors (particularly, comorbidities such as diabetes type 2, HIV, hypertension, and obesity) that increase the severity and risk of mortality after infection in Africa. Imputed public health response measures (especially, lockdowns and safe hygiene practices) contributed significantly to minimizing the role of these socio-ecological factors on the rate of SARS-CoV-2 transmission. Additionally, health system responses, such as surveillance and effective case management, aim to mitigate the effects of these biophysical factors. These are complemented using available vaccines, which enhance antibody development and thereby reduce the severity of the disease. Notwithstanding, the observed relatively fewer dead cases in the African region vis-à-vis other regions of the world may be linked to natural availability and socioeconomic access to phyto-genic foods, as well as food safety and healthy nutritional practices (Gesese *et al.*, 2021; Kong *et al.*, 2021; Tsori and Granek, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Bigna and Noubiap, 2019; Nachega *et al.*, 2021).

2. Phyto-genic foods rich in flavonoids and antioxidants to help fight against COVID-19 by targeting the virus and boosting the immune system

Clinically, COVID-19 infection induces chronic respiratory complications due to the storm of cytokines produced following the activation of viral proteins. The number of studies published on recent SARS-Cov2 infection is not high, adding to the absence of an effective treatment despite the increasing number of contaminations. This is probably because the viral strain was recently identified and has evolved evasive strategies to escape immune defenses and suppress interferon response in infected cells (Li and Xu, 2010). In addition, the disease is characterized by an upregulation of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IP-10, and MCP-1 in tissues and serum, and a massive infiltration of inflammatory cells such as macrophages in infected tissues (Li and Xu, 2010). Unfortunately, due to the lack of available animal models to mimic the clinical manifestations of SARS-Cov2, the development of studies on the disease remains a challenge. In consequence, no treatment has been found and this opens new ways for discovery of safe and effective drugs to stop the pandemic.

Natural compounds including phytochemicals and medicinal plants appear to be a promising option to fight against COVID-19. In Africa, several reports from scientists using medicinal plants alone or in combination with antibiotics indicated satisfactory effects in the treatment of thousands of COVID-19 patients. It is well established that phytochemicals present in foods contain interesting natural substances such as flavonoids with antioxidant properties which can boost the immune system and protect the host against SARS-Cov2 infection. Indeed, flavonoids are widely distributed in fruits, teas, and vegetables and are therefore accessible to the entire population. The beneficial effects of flavonoids on human health are mainly due to their reported antioxidant activity and their inhibition of key enzymes involved in the pathogenesis of several diseases. Moreover, they have the advantage of showing good bioavailability, good absorption, and minimal toxicity. A low antioxidant capacity has been reported in patients suffering from immunodeficiency diseases. For instance, vitamin C has emerged as an option due to its potential to reduce inflammation in the lungs since clinical studies showed that high doses of vitamin C provide certain protection against viral infection (Cheng, 2020). In addition, plant antioxidants act by modulating the signal of transduction factors and cytokine production in immune cells and may be used to evacuate the body from the trash of the virus and other reactive oxygen species produced during infection.

Fortunately, in the fight against COVID-19, several flavonoids are reported to boost the immune system and directly inhibit viral components necessary for its replication. For instance, quercetin and epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) are known as immune response enhancers that boost antibody production and cytotoxicity of natural killer cells against tumors (Martínez *et al.*, 2019). Another report pointed out the protective effect of flavonoids against upper respiratory tract infections (Somerville *et al.*, 2016). This is the case with green tea whose efficacy in boosting innate immunity and inhibiting upper respiratory tract infections was demonstrated (Hamer, 2007). The *in silico* approach is also actively used with molecular docking to demonstrate the potential binding of flavonoids on SARS-Co2 protein components. This is the case of luteolin, the main flavonoid of honeysuckle which was found to bind with a high affinity to P1pro, the main protease of SARS-Cov2 (Macchiagodena *et al.*, 2020). Other flavonoids including herbacetin, rhoifolin, and pectolonarin were reported to efficiently block the enzymatic activity of SARS-Cov2 3CLpro (Jo *et al.*, 2020). Myricetin and scutellarin also showed efficient inhibition of SARS-Cov helicase protein *in vitro* by inhibiting its ATPase activity (Yu *et al.*, 2012). Hesperidin and naringin are highly present in mandarin and sweet orange and are known for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects. Interestingly, both flavonoids were reported to bind angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), the receptor responsible for viral uptake in human cells (Cheng *et al.*, 2020).

Medicinal plants and constituent flavonoid compounds from Chinese medicine have shown promising results for SARS-Cov2 potential treatment so far. This is the case of Glycyrrhizin which is reported to inhibit the replication of SARS-associated coronaviruses *in vitro* (Cinatl *et al.*, 2003; However *et al.*, 2005). Moreover, high doses of the drug have been used in clinical trials and were reported to be effective for SARS treatment (Lu *et al.*, 2003; Wu *et al.*, 2004).

herperidin, a flavonoid found in citrus fruits and a well-known inhibitor of ACE2 is reported to block the infection of SARS-Cov2 (Chen and Du, 2020) and cleaved 3CLpro in cell-based assays (Lin *et al.*, 2005). Baicalin, another flavone, showed antiviral activities against 10 clinical isolates of SARS-Cov (Chen *et al.*, 2004). Finally, quercetin demonstrated antiviral effect by inhibiting 3CLpro of SARS-Cov (Chen *et al.*, 2006) and by blocking the entry of SARS-Cov into host cells (Wu *et al.*, 2004). From all the above, it appears that the presence of antioxidants in fruits and foods constitutes an interesting source of low-cost phytochemicals against the virus.

3. Good/healthy food safety and nutritional practices that can boost the immune system and enhance safety in the eyes of COVID-19

The COVID-19 health crisis is creating a range of unique and individual impacts—from food access issues to income disruptions, emotional distress, and beyond. Many ways have been suggested for the prevention and reduction of COVID-19. In addition to all the recommendations, protection against infection and management of the infected is to boost the individual's immune system. A good immune system will help to fight against the virus. Thus, if an individual is exposed to the virus, he may be able to resolve it without getting symptomatic and if already symptomatic, it will help to reduce viral load till convalescence. During the coronavirus infection like any other viral infection, the immunity of the person becomes a top priority. The boost of immunity requires eating a nutritious diet because the immune system relies on a steady supply of nutrients to work well. When the immune system functions optimally, it can help to keep a person healthy and render a sense of control in an uncertain time.

As much as there is yet no documented concrete evidence for defined dietary factors nor is there any one identified food that is guaranteed to boost the immune system specifically against the coronavirus, several foods have been suggested that can help boost immunity during COVID-19. Some of these are basil, turmeric, ginger, herbs, and spices like celery, and coconut oil because of its Lauric acid and caprylic acid content and vitamin C found in citrus fruits and peppers (Tripathi, 2020; Zickel, 2020). Most of these foods are supposed to provide nutrients such as good quality protein, hydration, vitamins especially, the Bs, C, A, D, and E as well as minerals such as iron, zinc, magnesium, and selenium which help a lot in improving immunity. These nutrients should better be taken in whole foods rather than supplements. Therefore, eating a nutritious healthy diet is paramount for COVID-19 patients, as well as healthy individuals who may pick up the virus, and care must be taken to ensure the safety of any food consumed.

Food Safety describes handling, preparation, and food storage to preserve the quality of food to prevent contamination and food-borne illnesses. Food safety is a global concern that covers a variety of different areas of everyday life. It includes Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of food handlers (Sani, 2014), meal planning, cooking, and eating of foods.

In 1963, FAO and WHO jointly founded the Codex Alimentarius Commission to ensure international harmonization of food standards to protect consumer health. Dietary Guidelines for Americans recommends four basic food safety principles: clean, separate, chill, and cook (Dietary Guidelines, 2020). World Health Organization (WHO) introduced the 'Five Keys to Safer Food' in 2001 (Fontannaz-Aujoulat *et al.*, 2019; WHO, 2006; WHO, 2020) which are relevant both in developing and developed countries with target populations being Governments, Health Educators, Risk communicators, Food handlers and Consumers. The five keys are to keep food clean, separate raw and cooked food, cook food thoroughly, store food at a safe temperature, and use safe water and raw materials in food preparations. All these interventions are to ensure good food practices from production point to consumption. However, as of today, only 146 countries are using the five keys (WHO, 2020), and the materials have been translated into 68 languages (Onogore *et al.*, 2021)

Measures to control the spread and infections of COVID-19 should take into consideration the interventions of all the bodies on food safety and WHO. While the developed world may probably be doing well, the same cannot be said about the developing nations with their many challenges. Cleanliness has been emphasized at every point in the management and reducing viral load in COVID-19 (Onofre *et al.*, 2021). Lack of access to clean portable water is a common phenomenon and availability of adequate safe water is uncommon. Water is a critical item in food preparation and handling and the most common contaminant of foods. If water is contaminated, it can pose a serious health risk to consumers and if used to over-dilute foods, it reduces the nutritional value of foods like milk and fruit juices (Handford *et al.*, 2016). Regular and constant electricity supply is also necessary to meet the fourth WHO key for food safety, otherwise, there will be losses due to food spoilage. For COVID-19, food must be properly cooked. If food is not cooked well, pathogens may not be destroyed. However, overcooking vegetables will also destroy heat-labile vitamins. This will not be good for COVID-19 cases who need a lot of nutrients to boost their immunity.

Safe food practices and proper food hygiene apply to homes, restaurants, and food service workers as well as food business owners. Restaurants, cafeterias, and bars have been reported as the most likely locations where food poisoning can occur, homes have also been found to present with food contamination (Redmond and Griffith, 2003). Physical/social distancing has been emphasized in reducing the transmission of COVID-19. While this does not apply to the food itself, the risk may be associated with the kitchen, food preparation, and delivery staff. In these days of COVID-19, it could be necessary to limit the number of staff in the kitchen and/or food preparation area. The workstations and food preparation areas should be spaced out. Takeaway restaurants should be conscious of the maintenance of appropriate temperatures for food transport and delivery to meet WHO's key for food safety issues. Since COVID-19 can remain on surfaces for up to 24 hours, food packaging should be handled in line with usual food safety practices, and upon reception consumers should discard cardboard packaging. For

food businesses and ventures, contactless payments should be considered to avoid touching money.

Although information about knowledge attitudes and practices of food handlers on food safety is available, food service establishments still present with limited awareness (**Redmond and Griffith, 2003**) about food-handling behaviours. Staff should undergo proper training in food safety constantly and regular screening of employees for the virus should be done. Infected workers should not be allowed to handle food and good hygiene practices should be maintained around open foods. It is very important to make sure the food that COVID-19 patients eat is not contaminated with other pathogens, toxins, parasites, and chemicals. An infected person needs to have access to nutritious safe and healthy foods. At this time, the individual cannot afford the luxury of co-morbidity with food poisoning since this will further complicate the already poor state of health and can thus be lethal.

Conclusion

Irrespective of the region, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human health, societies, and economies is still painful. The COVID-19 burden is uneven and the variation in incidences across countries is driven by socio-ecological factors, likewise, the severity and risk of mortality after infection are influenced by biophysical factors. Imputed public health response measures and health system responses contributed significantly to minimizing the above factors. Notwithstanding, the observed relatively fewer dead cases in the African region vis-à-vis other regions of the world may be linked to natural availability and socio-economic access to phyto-genic foods, as well as food safety and healthy nutritional practices. This review has briefly discussed the roles of phyto-genic food safety and nutritional practices vis-à-vis the fight against COVID-19. Phyto-genic foods appear to be a promising option to fight against COVID-19. The satisfactory use of medicinal plants in the treatment of thousands of COVID-19 patients has been well documented. Fortunately, in the fight against COVID-19, several flavonoids are reported to boost the immune system and directly inhibit viral components necessary for its replication. When considering that a good immune system helps to fight against the virus, the boost of immunity requires eating a nutritious diet as the immune system relies on a steady supply of nutrients to work well. These nutrients are better taken whole (than in supplements). Furthermore, food Safety including knowledge, attitudes, and practices of food handlers, meal planning, cooking, and eating of foods is vital to maintaining/preserving these foods for whole nutrient intake.

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